

Radiometric Investigation of the Flotation of Egyptian Iron Ores

SELIM F. ESTEFAN

Metallurgy Dept., National Research Centre, Cairo

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Reverse anionic flotation of Aswan hematite ores revealed that good results may be obtained by using the particle size $-0.1+0.02$ mm. Scrubbing with sulphuric acid seemed to be a prerequisite prior to flotation. 10.5 is the optimum pH value for good recovery and high grade iron concentrate at a collector : activator molar ratio of 1:2. The activating effect of the alkaline-earth cations increases in the order : $\text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Sr}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$, which is the same order of their increased adsorbability onto quartz surface, the order of shifting the zeta-potential of quartz particles to less negative values and the order of enhancing the abstraction of sodium oleate by quartz particles. At high pH values, higher than 12, recovery falls down due to the competition between OH^- and oleate ions, due to the formation of colloidal silica as a result of increased solubility of surface silicic acid and due to competition between Na^+ and the activating cations at high $[\text{M}^+]/[\text{M}^{2+}]$ ratios.

Starting with a feed ore assaying about 32.8% Fe, a concentrate having 52.5% Fe with a recovery of 83% could be obtained for the first rougher. A schematic flow sheet for the beneficiation of Aswan iron ores is given.

THE siliceous red iron ores of Aswan consist of relatively impure hematite associated with siliceous gangue materials. Much of the ore is of the oolitic type, composed of spherules of hematite and rounded quartz grains. Sink-float fractionation and roasting and magnetic separation of typical red ores indicated that rejection of quartz and gangue minerals is all that can be expected from beneficiation.

The first attempts to apply cationic flotation of the siliceous gangue from neutral pulps did not succeed. The ready flotability of the quartz during soap flotation of the hematite indicated that quartz and granular silicate minerals in the red iron ores were naturally activated to flotation.

Radioactive tracer techniques were applied to investigate the activating effect of the alkaline-earth cations on quartz particles using the radionuclides Ca^{45} , Sr^{89} and Ba^{140} . Co-adsorption of the radionuclides Na^{22} and Ca^{45} , from highly alkaline media, on quartz particles could emphasize that the competitive nature between M^+ and M^{2+} cations on the quartz surface at high $[\text{M}^+]/[\text{M}^{2+}]$ ratio is one of the factors responsible for the serious drop in flotability of quartz at such high pH values.

Preliminary reverse anionic flotation tests have given encouraging results for concentration of the low grade Aswan iron ore that heretofore proved difficult to concentrate by conventional flotation procedures. The investigation was extended to cover a variety of the main factors affecting anionic flotation of gangue minerals.

Experimental

Preparation of ore samples

Lumps of hand picked quartz, from Aswan pegmatite quartz veins, were ground and the size fraction $-0.037+0.01$ mm. was selected for adsorption measurements

after treatment with hot concentrated hydrochloric acid followed by thorough washing with distilled water and then kept in a Pyrex glass bottle under de-ionized water. The size distribution of the product, assaying 99.5% SiO_2 , was determined by elutriation and indicated that more than 71-73% of the quartz particles were within the size range $-0.037+0.025$ mm. The specific surface area, measured by krypton adsorption methods, was found to be $1400 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$.

The low grade oolitic hematite from Aswan was crushed in a laboratory jaw crusher, sampled and ground to pass 100 mesh in a laboratory disc mill. The ground product was wet screened to -0.1 mm. The oversize was ground in a rod mill for five minutes at 1:1 solid/liquid ratio and then wet screened and the collected -0.1 mm. fraction was scrubbed with dilute sulphuric acid and deslimed to $+0.02$ mm. and used as the feed to the flotation circuit. Chemical analysis of the ore showed that it contains 32.8% Fe and 32.6% acid insolubles. The particle size analysis of the fraction $-0.1+0.02$ mm. was determined by elutriation and indicated that more than 65% of the sample was in the range $-0.08+0.04$ mm.

Adsorption tests

Generally, the adsorption of the activating alkaline-earth cations was computed from the concentrations before and after conditioning with the quartz particles. For this purpose, the isotopic dilution technique¹ has been applied. One ml of each of the tagged 0.01 M solutions of the chlorides of Ca^{45} , Sr^{89} or Ba^{140} were diluted to hundred fold and 1 ml aliquots were evaporated on standard aluminium planchets and counted by an end-window G. M. counter and the specific activity S_0 was calculated in each case. For the adsorption tests, varying amounts of each tagged solution were diluted to 100 ml, added to 5 g quartz samples, the pH adjusted to 10.5 and conditioned for 1 hr at 30°. One ml aliquots of each filtrate were evaporated on planchets

and counted. From the corresponding corrected count rate, the specific activity S_1 was determined. In this case, the weights for example, W_1 , contained in this 1 ml aliquot was determined from the relation :

$$W_1 = S_1 (W_0/S_0)$$

where W_0 is the weight of the sample whose specific activity is S_0 . The equilibrium concentration in each case was calculated and hence the amount adsorbed was determined, from which the adsorption density was calculated. The adsorption isotherms were then plotted.

General procedure of flotation test

50 g of the feed ore were pulped with water at a solid/liquid ratio of 1:3. Conditioning was carried out in the flotation cell :

- i) with the modifying agent, NaOH, and activator, CaCl_2 , for five minutes ;
- ii) with the depressant, pearl starch (0.12 lb/ton), added as 0.1% aqueous solution for 5 minutes to depress iron oxides ;
- iii) with the collector, sodium oleate, and a constant amount (0.5 lb/ton) of Aerofroth 77 for 5 min. till the pulp appeared to be flocculated ;
- iv) flotation was then carried out at a solid/liquid ratio of 1:5.

Investigation of the main factors affecting flotation process

a) The particle size of the feed plays an important role in the flotation process. Much of the siliceous gangue is so finely disseminated in the hematite that grinding beyond the limits of commercial methods would be required for liberation. The particle size ranges used in this investigation were -0.1 , -0.15 and -0.2 mm., all fractions being deslimed to $+0.02$ mm. Flotation was carried out using 3.5 lb oleate/ton, 2.2 lb calcium chloride/ton and 0.5 lb frother/ton at $pH=10.5$.

b) Desliming is prerequisite for successful flotation since slimes have a detrimental effect on flotation process. In presence of slimes, the froths were voluminous and selectivity was poor. Tests on deslimed charges gave better results. A constant upper size limit of -0.1 mm. was maintained and the feed was deslimed to $+0.02$, $+0.015$ or $+0.01$ mm. and the results were compared with an undeslimed sample. Desliming to $+0.02$ mm, seemed to give the best results, so the fraction $-0.1+0.02$ mm. was selected for the subsequent tests.

c) Acid scrubbing is a process by which the surface of the floatable mineral can be cleaned so as to be in direct contact with the activating and collecting agents. This is particularly important in the selective flotation of quartz from hematite. Varying amounts of sulphuric acid ranging from 4.4 to 21.6 lb. H_2SO_4 /ton of ore were used. The maximum improvement of the grade of concentrate seems to be attained after scrubbing with 7 lb. of acid/ton. In the subsequent tests scrubbing with 7 lb. of acid/ton was always carried out prior to flotation.

d) It is well known that activated quartz floats in alkaline media. The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on flotation was therefore investigated within the

pH range 9-12 using sodium hydroxide as the modifier. It was found that 10.5 is the optimum pH and so the pulp was kept at this pH value in the subsequent tests.

e) The collector used in these tests was pure sodium oleate, added as 1% aqueous solution during the conditioning step. Varying concentrations in the range 1.7-5.3 lb. oleate/ton were used with a constant activator concentration of 2.2 lb calcium chloride/ton. It was found that 3.5 lb oleate/ton gave a maximum grade of iron concentrate.

f) With a constant collector concentration of 3.5 lb oleate/ton (5g. equiv./ton), the effect of the concentration of the activating cations was tested by using 0.1 M solution of the chlorides of calcium, strontium or barium in the concentration range 5-20 g. ion of the cation/ton. The optimum amount of activator, under the specified conditions, was found to be 10 g. ion/ton for a maximum grade of concentrate.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption tests

Figure 1 indicates that the adsorption density of the alkaline-earth cations onto quartz surface increases in the order : $\text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Sr}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$. It was concluded² that the adsorbability of these cations is directly proportional to the reciprocals of the radii of the hydrated cations.

The question of the state of adsorbed ions in the mercury electrolyte double layer as discussed by Grahame reveals that the anions become dehydrated and are held, partly by covalent bonds, in what he termed "the inner Helmholtz plane" next to the mercury surface. On the other hand, the hydrated cations are seemed to be held in "the outer Helmholtz plane". It seems probable that in the quartz-electrolyte double layer, the adsorbed alkaline-earth cations are hydrated. Accordingly, they may be considered to be electrostatically held in the outer Helmholtz plane.

It is therefore, expected that the activating effect of these cations during oleate flotation of quartz increases in the order : $\text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Sr}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$.

Fig. 1 : Adsorption Isotherms onto Quartz.

Flotation tests

1) *Effect of particle size* : The choice of suitable size involves a compromise between the recovery and the grade of iron concentrate. The overall rate of flotation is usually a maximum for intermediate size of particles. Liberation studies of Aswan iron ores indicated that the degree of liberation is not very high. It can be seen from Figure 2 that on decreasing the upper size limit of the feed, the grade of iron concentrate and even its recovery were higher. This observation does not mean that more liberation is attained at the finer sizes, but rather difficult for coarser particles to float. Although the iron concentrate has a higher iron content when the maximum feed size is -0.1 mm., a detailed economic consideration is necessary before deciding which maximum size is more advantageous. Possibly, for this ore which is easily ground, finer grinding will not be costly especially in an area where cheap electric power is available. However, the amount of slimes produced on grinding has to be taken into consideration if it is not benefited by selective flocculation followed by flotation.

Fig. 2 : Effect of Particle Size.

2) *Effect of desliming* : The tendency of hematite to slime is well exhibited by Aswan iron ore. Slimes play a decisive role in iron-quartz flotation separation. A hematite coating on the quartz particles will seriously hinder the surface differentiation between quartz and hematite. Slime-coating is better understood in the light of the electric double layer concept and can be prevented by adding a potential-determining ion which makes the surface charge of both minerals the same. Then the repulsive force, being greater than the attractive van der Waals force, stops the formation of slime-coatings. Although the potential-determining ions of both quartz and hematite are H^+ and OH^- , the slime problem still prevents successful separation of quartz and hematite even at high pH values (10.5). The data in Table (1) indicates that desliming to 0.01 mm. has a greater influence on the grade of iron concentrate than desliming to 0.015 or 0.02 mm. but the recovery increases markedly as the grade falls slightly. It appears that desliming to 0.02 mm. gives the best results as regards recovery and at the same time the grade is sufficiently high.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DESLIMING ON FLOTATION PROCESS

deslimed fraction mm.	assay of concentrate		assay of tailings		% recovery
	%Fe	%insol.	%Fe	%insol.	
---	35.6	33.6	31.7	38.0	82.5
-0.01	49.2	12.7	23.8	47.5	61.6
-0.015	48.1	16.5	20.7	50.4	69.7
-0.02	47.1	17.4	19.6	55.2	76.8

3) *Effect of acid scrubbing* : The work of Pol'kin and Andreev³ on the effect of sulphuric acid on the physico-chemical and flotation properties of various minerals has revealed that, in most cases, acid treatment shifted the electrokinetic potential towards the positive side and thus enhancing the attachment of oleate ions to the mineral surface. However, this effect cannot be responsible for the beneficial effect of acid scrubbing on the flotation of quartz from Aswan iron ores. Any shift towards more positive or less negative potential renders the process of activation of quartz more difficult. It is more likely that sulphuric acid dissolves the fine hematite slimes, or at least prevents their attachment to the quartz particles. Figure 3 shows that the effect of the amount of acid used in scrubbing is not very marked and this should be decided on the basis of economic considerations.

Fig. 3 : Effect of Acid Scrubbing.

4) *Effect of pH* : Activation of quartz by polyvalent cations is best accomplished in alkaline pulps. The zeta-potential of quartz becomes more negative on increasing the OH^- ion concentration, reaching a maximum at about $10^{-4}M$ i. e. about pH 10. This apparently explains the change in the grade of the iron concentrate which reached a maximum at pH 10.5 (Figure 4) if it is assumed that the negative charge determines the extent of activation and consequently the hydrophobization of the surface attained by the subsequent fixation of oleate ions to the activated surface.

Fig. 4 : Effect of pH.

Since H^+ and OH^- ions are the potential-determining ions, the depressant effect of higher concentrations of OH^- ions has been assumed⁴ due to competition between OH^- and oleate ions for the activated quartz surface, shifting to the left for the equilibrium.

and when OH^- ions replace Ol^- ions, the mineral surface becomes hydrophilic and is depressed. However, at $pH > 11$, the formation of colloidal silica results due to the increasing solubility of surface silicic acid. The quartz surface is now in a state of dynamic equilibrium⁵ which results in lowering the activation extent and consequently its flotability.

On the other hand, it was suggested⁶ that depression of quartz at high pH values occurs by competition between Na^+ and Ba^{2+} ions for space in the Stern layer since OH^- and Ol^- ions function in completely different manner at the quartz surface. Co-adsorption of Na^+ and Ca^{2+} ions, using the radionuclides Na^{22} and Ca^{45} , at pH 12 and at different $[Na^+]/[Ca^{2+}]$ ratios confirmed the dependence of the competitive nature between M^+ and M^{2+} ions onto quartz surface upon the ratio of their concentrations⁷.

5) Effect of collector concentration : The fall in the grade of iron concentrate after reaching a maximum

Fig. 5 : Effect of Collector Concentration.

at an oleate concentration of 3.5 lb/ton (Figure 5) is sometimes observed when the collecting power is lost at higher collector concentration. For our specific system, two main causes may be responsible for the drop in the grade of iron concentrate at high oleate concentrations. Firstly, armouring of air bubbles by adsorbed collector, Leja and Schulman⁸ elaborated this view by assuming that adhesion of the mineral to air bubbles is prevented when the films at the air/solution and solid/solution interfaces are highly condensed. Secondly, the formation of micellae on the surface of the mineral and its subsequent hydration. This appears to be more likely since the c. m. c. of sodium oleate is 0.7-0.9 mM. per litre⁹. It is apparent that the depressant action of the collector becomes evident at concentrations higher than the c. m. c. and in some cases, attachment of air bubbles is prevented even at concentrations considerably lower than the c. m. c. since the surface concentration of collector may be considerably greater than the bulk concentration.

6) Effect of activator concentration : The results in Figure 6 show that the activating effect of the alkaline-earth cations increases in the order: Ca^{2+} -activation < Sr^{2+} -activation < Ba^{2+} -activation. This order is the same as the order of increased adsorbability of the cations, the order of decreasing the negativity of the zeta-potential of quartz particles in the presence of the cations and the order of their effect on enhancing the abstraction of sodium oleate by quartz particles⁷.

Fig. 6 : Effect of Activator Concentration. (A grade and B recovery)

In a comparative study of the desorption of oleate ions⁵, initially adsorbed from a solution of the same oleate concentration, it was found that adsorption was greater on barite than on celestite but more oleate was desorbed from the latter than from the former. Similarly, more oleate was adsorbed on strontianite than on calcite but desorption of oleate from calcite was greater than from strontianite. Oleate ions are not only adsorbed on the surface of these minerals but also in the diffuse double layer¹⁰. This observation agrees well with the results of the present investigation indicating that oleate ions attached to the Ba^{2+} -activated quartz are more strongly held than that attached to Sr^{2+} -activated quartz and the latter more strongly held than that attached to Ca^{2+} -activated quartz.

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Infrared spectroscopy¹¹ has shown evidence of chemisorption of oleate on calcite and barite, although not all the bands identified were identical with those of bulk calcium oleate. Besides chemisorption there was evidence of physically adsorbed oleic acid.

The observed gradual decrease in the iron recovery after reaching a clear maximum attained at the same activating cations concentration (10 g. ion/ton) is due to the decrease of the ratio oleate/activator on increasing the activator concentration. The maximum recovery seems to be attained in all cases when the molar concentration is 1 collector : 2 activator. This ratio has no relation to any stoichiometric compound. The same general conclusion of Gaudin and Chang¹² was that the critical collector coating necessary for flotation is much less complete than that of the activator.

Micellae formation of oleate ions adds complications to the process of oleate fixation to the activated quartz surface, since the oleate concentration in all the tests was near c. m. c. Infrared spectra¹³ gave evidence of micellae formation of oleate on the surface of fluorite, calcite and barite at pH values higher than 9.5.

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Fig. 7 : Schematic flow sheet for beneficiation of Aswan iron ore.

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